

A Case study to explore the challenges faced by Transgender Community, Solan, H.P.

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Abstract-

BACKGROUND: Transgenders is an ancient part of human civilization. Transgender individuals have long faced societal discrimination, exclusion, and prejudice due to their gender identity and expression. Transgender individuals have existed throughout history and across cultures, but their experiences have often been hidden or marginalized. It is only in recent decades that transgender rights and issues have gained greater visibility and understanding.

AIM: The aim of the study was to explore the challenges faced by transgender community residing at Kotla Nala district Solan, Himachal Pradesh.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY: A Qualitative research approach was used by using case study method used and consecutive sampling technique was used to select the sample. Sample size was five transgenders. The study was conducted at Kotla Nala near Degree College, district Solan. Data was collected by using socio-demographic variable, performa to evaluate major challenges faced by transgender community and in-depth semi structured interview. The collected data was analyzed by using thematic analysis technique, field notes were taken and data was recorded in audio and video manner.

RESULT: Findings of the study revealed that out of 5 study samples, in context with social problems, majority of study subjects i.e., 3(60%) had faced the verbal and physical abuse followed by 2(40%) study subject were thrown out of the family, 4(80%) of the study subject have faced discrimination at school or educational settings, 4(80%) of the study subject got threatened by others, 3(60%) of the study subject faced rejection by peers, 3(60%) of the study subjects felt isolated from society, 2(40%) of the study subjects had faced issues in using public toilet, 1(20%) of the study subject had faced bullying. With regards to the economic problems, majority of the study subjects i.e., 3(60%) had lack of adequate education due to lack of financial support from the family, 4(80%) of the study subjects had faced problem of lack of employment opportunities. In context with the physical and psychological problem, majority of the study subject i.e., 5(100%) had faced hormonal imbalance, anxiety, depression, suicidal ideations. With regards to the political problems, majority of the study subjects i.e., 5(100%) had not got the adequate state support. In context with the legal problem, majority of the study subject i.e., 5(100%) had difficulty in child adoption followed by right to free speech violation.

CONCLUSION: This study concluded that transgenders faced many challenges in life such as discrimination, threatened by others, rejection by peers, lack of adequate education, depression, social ideations etc.

Key words: Transgenders, Transgenders challenges faced, discrimination, gender expression.

INTRODUCTION:

People of transgender category lives with the community named as trans community. The trans community is incredibly diverse. Some trans people identify as trans men or trans women, while others may describe themselves as non-binary, genderqueer, gender non-conforming, agender, bigender or other identities that reflect their personal experience. Some of them take hormones or have surgery as part of their transition, while others may change our pronouns or appearance.¹

The word transgender has its roots in Greek which means “keeper of the bed”. It can be inferred that Vedic culture recognized three genders. The Vedas 1500-500 BC describes individuals as belonging to one of three separate categories, according to one’s nature or prakriti. Various texts suggest that third sex individuals were well known in pre-modern Indian and included male bodied or female bodied people as well as intersexual.²

The Global prevalence of gender dysphoria according the According to *DSM-5-TR* which was published on 9 may 2022 is 0.005–0.014% for adult natal males and 0.002-0.003% for adult natal females. In Europe, 1 per 30,000 adult males and 1 per 100,000 adult females seek sexual reassignment surgery (SRS). In children; gender dysphoria is 2–4.5

times more common among natal boys than among natal girls. In adolescents, the male-to-female ratio is closer to parity. In adults, the male-to-female ratio is generally weighted toward natal males, ranging from 1:1 to 6.1:1; however, it tends toward natal females in both Japan (1:2.2) and Poland (1:3.4).³

Transgender challenges is not something that is unheard According to a study conducted by the National Human Rights Commission in 2018, 96%transgenders are denied jobs and are forced to take low paying or undignified work for livelihood like badhais, sex work and begging. The first-ever study on the rights of transgenders also revealed that about 92% of transgenders are deprived of the right to participate in any form of economic activity in the country, with even qualified ones refused jobs. Among the respondents, around 89 per cent of transgenders said there are no jobs for even qualified ones. 50-60 per cent never attended schools and those who did face severe discrimination, according to the report. Irrespective to initiative taken by the government still 52% transgenders were harassed by their classmates and 15%by teachers, forcing them to discontinue their studies. Only 6%transgenders were employed in private sectors or NGOs, back then, while the monthly income of only 1 % transgenders was noted to be above Rs.25,000; the majority-26.35% earn between Rs. 10,000-Rs.15,000.⁴

According to the article posted by UNAIDS organization on 31st March 2023 regarding the job difficulties that transgenders have to face. They posted an interview of Ratrish Saha who is a transgender woman from Kolkata, India. She said even with seven years' work experience, she was anxious about applying for a new job last year. She further said "Finding a job is never easy being a transgender woman. I would get rejected with statements like 'currently no LGBT hiring is going on' or 'we do not have facilities to accommodate a trans individual in our office'," she recalled. But through the Transgender Welfare Equity and Empowerment Trust or TWEET Foundation, she was paired with suitable opportunities in corporations that have received sensitivity training. She soon landed the position of associate consultant for Siemens Technology in Bangalore.⁵

As most of the studies, articles suggest the prevalence of discrimination, harassment, and violence against transgender people specifically because of their gender identity; and To examine such experiences across multiple domains of life raised as areas of concern among expert, including health care, education, employment, political participation, we consider it as our responsibility.

2. METHODS AND MATERIALS:

2.1 RESEARCH APPROACH DESIGN: Qualitative research approach with a multiple case design was used for the study.

2.2 SETTING:

- **For pilot study:** Pilot study was conducted at transgender community residing at Krishna Nagar/ Ladakhi Mohalla, Shimla.
- **For main study:** Final study was conducted among transgender community residing at kotla nala district Solan.
- **Target population:** The target population of the study was community people residing at Kotla Nala, Solan.
- **Accessible population:** Accessible population for final study was transgender community residing at Kotla Nala, district Solan.

2.4 SAMPLE AND SAMPLE TECHNIQUE: Selection of the subject was done by using consecutive sampling technique. Sample size were 5 transgender people.

2.5 DATA COLLECTION TOOL(S) AND TECHNIQUE:

Based on objective of the study the tool developed are as following:

Three research tools were developed by researcher such as socio-demographic variables, Performa to evaluate the challenges faced by the transgender community and in-depth semi structured interview.

TOOL 1: SOCIO – DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLE SHEET

This tool was used to assess the socio–demographic variables of the Transgender community.

TOOL 2: PERFORMA TO EVALUATE THE CHALLENGES FACED BY THE TRANSGENDER COMMUNITY

This tool was used to evaluate the major challenges that transgender faced in their life.

TOOL 3: IN- DEPTH SEMI- STRUCTURED INTERVIEW

This tool included in-depth semi-structured interview, where open ended questions were asked from the selected study subject.

2.6 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION:

All the participants were informed that their participation in study was voluntary and they can refuse to participate and withdraw from the study at any time.

Apart from this, written consent was taken from head of the transgender community named Priya Mahant (Guru ji). Confidentiality and anonymity of the study subject was also been take care of.

TABLE 1: Depicts frequency and percentage distribution of study subjects regarding challenges faced by transgender community as per socio-demographic variables

N=5

S. No.	Socio-demographic variable	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1.	Age (in years)		
a.	Up to 17	0	0
b.	18-24	0	0
c.	25-34	2	40
d.	>35	3	60
2.	Sex assigned at birth		
a.	Male	0	0
b.	Female	0	0
c.	Third gender	5	100
3.	What did you feel your gender should be		
a.	Male or masculine	0	0
b.	Female or feminine	5	100
c.	Both male and female	0	0
d.	Neither male or female	0	0
e.	Not known	0	0
4.	What gender do you currently live		
a.	Transmen	0	0
b.	Transwomen	5	100
c.	Intersex	0	0
5.	Religion		
a.	Hindu	5	100
b.	Muslim	0	0
c.	Sikh	0	0
d.	Other	0	0
6.	Place of living		
a.	own house	5	100
b.	Leased	0	0
c.	rented with other	0	0
d.	shared with other	0	0
7.	Civil status		
a.	Single	5	100
b.	Married	0	0
c.	Divorced	0	0
d.	Cohabiting	0	0
e.	Others	0	0
8.	Educational status		
a.	No formal education	2	40
b.	Primary education	1	20
c.	Secondary education	1	20
d.	Graduate	1	20
e.	Postgraduate	0	0
f.	Others	0	0
9.	Occupational status		
a.	Student	0	0
b.	Private servant	0	0
c.	Self employed	0	0
d.	Others (traditional dancing in birthday ceremonies and marriages)	5	100
e.	Retired	0	0
f.	No specific job	0	0
10.	Economic status (monthly)		
a.	5000-10000	0	0
b.	11000-20000	0	0

S. No.	Socio-demographic variable	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
c.	21000-40000	0	0
d.	41000-50000	5	100
e.	>50000	0	0
11.	How many people live in participants house		
a.	2-5	0	0
b.	6-10	5	100
c.	>10	0	0
d.	No one	0	0
12.	At what age did you first become aware that you are transgender or gender non-conforming.		
a.	<9 year	2	40
b.	10-12 year	0	0
c.	13-14year	3	60
d.	15-16 year	0	0
e.	>16 year	0	0
13.	At what age did you first tell another person that you are transgender or gender non-conforming		
a.	<9 year	2	40
b.	10-12 year	0	0
c.	13-14year	3	60
d.	15-16 year	0	0
e.	>16 year	0	0
14.	who have you told that you are transgender or gender not conforming		
a.	Family	4	80
b.	Friends	1	20
c.	Colleague	0	0
d.	Teacher	0	0
e.	Other	0	0
15.	knowledge regarding the kind of resource provide by government to transgender community		
a.	don't know	5	100
b.	Know	0	0
16.	feel unsafe in society or didn't think that the government has made enough laws to protect the transgender community		
a.	Yes	5	100
b.	No	0	0
17.	Do you have any type of ID proof		
a.	Voter ID card	5	100
b.	Aadhar card	5	100
c.	Driving license	0	0
d.	PAN card	5	100
e.	Nothing	0	0
f.	Any other	0	0

Table no. 1 depict the frequency and percentage distribution of demographic variable with respect to age, sex assigned at birth, gender that they felt, gender they are living today, religion, place of living, civil status, educational status, occupational status, economic status, no. of participants living together, age at which they became aware of them being transgender, at which age did you tell other about you being transgender, to whom you have told about you being transgender, knowledge regarding resources that are provide by the government to them, if government has made enough laws for them and type of ID proof.

Table 2: Frequency and percentage distribution of challenges faced by the transgender community
N =5

S. No.	Challenges	Yes		No	
		Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1.	Social Problem				
a.	Verbal and physical abuse (harassment, exploitation, rape etc.)	3	(60%)	2	(40%)
b.	Thrown out of the family	2	(40%)	3	(60%)
c.	Discrimination at school/educational settings	4	(80%)	1	(20%)
d.	Threatened by others	4	(80%)	1	(20%)
e.	Rejection by peers	3	(60%)	2	(40%)
f.	Isolated from the society	3	(60%)	2	(40%)
g.	Bathroom issues for the use of public toilet	2	(40%)	3	(60%)
h.	Denial of the family property	4	(80%)	1	(20%)
i.	Bullying	1	(20%)	4	(80%)
2.	Economical Problem				
a.	Lack of adequate education due to lack of financial support from the family	3	(60%)	2	(40%)
b.	Lack of employment opportunities	4	(80%)	1	(20%)
c.	Forced into sex work or begging	0	-	5	(100%)
d.	Resigned from job without tolerating stigma and discrimination	0	-	5	(100%)
3.	Problems in Health Care Settings				
a.	Refusing to admit in health care settings due to specific gender identity	0	-	5	(100%)
b.	Denial of medical services due to specific gender identity	0	-	5	(100%)
c.	Sexual and reproductive health needs are often not addressed	0	-	5	(100%)
d.	Undergoes unnecessary examination because of specific gender identity	0	-	5	(100%)
4.	Physical and Psychological Problem				
a.	Hypertension	0	-	5	(100%)
b.	Diabetes	0	-	5	(100%)
c.	Hypothyroidism	0	-	5	(100%)
d.	Hyperthyroidism	0	-	5	(100%)
e.	Hormonal imbalance	5	(100%)	0	-
f.	Sexually transmitted diseases (HIV, AIDS, etc.)	0	-	5	(100%)
g.	Anxiety	5	(100%)	0	-
h.	Depression	5	(100%)	0	-
i.	Suicidal ideation	5	(100%)	0	-
j.	Other (specify)	0	-	5	100%
5.	Political Problems				
a.	Discrimination in issuing common government documents (such as voter ID cards, passports, PAN card, driving license, any other)	0	-	5	(100%)
b.	Lack of recognition for leadership	0	-	5	(100%)
c.	Not getting adequate state support (except Tamil Nadu because According to their policy, transgender people can access free sex reassignment surgery in government hospitals, free housing,	5	(100%)	0	-

	various citizenship documents, admission in government colleges with a full scholarship for higher studies and initiating income-generation programmers)				
6.	Legal Problems				
a.	Human and civil rights violation	0	-	5	(100%)
b.	Lack of recognition for marriage	0	-	5	(100%)
c.	Difficulty in child adoption	5	(100%)	0	-
d.	Violation in right to equal opportunities	0	-	5	(100%)
e.	Right to free speech violation	5	(100%)	5	(100%)

Table 2: Depicts that out of 5 study samples, in context with social problems, majority of study subjects i.e., 3(60%) had faced the verbal and physical abuse followed by 2(40%) study subject were thrown out of the family, 4(80%) of the study subject have faced discrimination at school or educational settings, 4(80%) of the study subject got threatened by others, 3(60%) of the study subject faced rejection by peers, 3(60%) of the study subjects felt isolated from society, 2(40%) of the study subjects had faced issues in using public toilet, 1(20%) of the study subject had faced bullying. With regards to the economic problems, majority of the study subjects i.e., 3(60%) had lack of adequate education due to lack of financial support from the family, 4(80%) of the study subjects had faced problem of lack of employment opportunities. In context with the physical and psychological problem, majority of the study subject i.e., 5(100%) had faced hormonal imbalance, anxiety, depression, suicidal ideations. With regards to the political problems, majority of the study subjects i.e., 5(100%) had not got the adequate state support. In context with the legal problem, majority of the study subject i.e., 5(100%) had difficulty in child adoption followed by right to free speech violation.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that the major challenges faced by transgender community were discrimination in school/educational settings, threatened by others, rejection by peers, lack of adequate education, lack of employment opportunities, hormonal imbalance, depression, suicidal ideations, not getting adequate state support, difficulty in child adoption, difficulty in making love relationships.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the result of study, following recommendations were made:

- A descriptive study can be conducted to assess the level of self esteem among the transgender people in selected area of Shimla, Himachal Pradesh.
- A quasi-experimental study can be conducted to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching program on self esteem among transgender person residing in Shimla, Himachal Pradesh.
- A descriptive study can be conducted to assess the prevalence of common health problems among the transgender person residing in Shimla, Himachal Pradesh.
- A co-relational study can be conducted to assess the association between suicidal attempts in connection to discrimination among transgender people residing at Shimla, Himachal Pradesh.
- A descriptive study can be conducted to assess the prevalence rate of suicidal ideation among transgender people residing at Shimla, Himachal Pradesh.

LIMITATIONS

Several limitations to the present study deserve considerations:

- Getting permission from the transgender community was quite difficult.
- Gaining trust and developing therapeutic relationship with transgenders were difficult for the researchers.
- Some of the study subjects were not that much interested in sharing their personal information.

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